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Supplementary material of article

Socio-environmental and economic impacts due to the disaster at Vale S.A. in
Brumadinho, MG, Brazil: a systematic review

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Abstract - Spreadsheet with the results of the scientific articles eligible in the systematic review, using the PRISMA methodology, carried out to identify scientific articles addressing the socio-environmental and economic impacts faced by fishermen and fish farmers around the Três Marias reservoir/MG/Brazil. Time frame of January 1, 2019 to May 22, 2023.

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N	Journal	Article title	Year	Authors	Objectives	Keywords	Main conclusions	Link (pdf)	Relevance (High, Medium, Low)
1	Neotropical Ichthyology	Negative impacts of mining on Neotropical freshwater fishes	2021	Valter M. Azevedo-Santos, Marlene S. Arcifa, Marcelo FG Brito, Angelo A. Agostinho, Robert M. Hughes, Jean RS Vitule, Daniel Simberloff, Julian D. Olden, Fernando M. Pelicice	This review gathered information on the main impacts of crude oil, gold, iron, copper and bauxite mining on aquatic ecosystems, with an emphasis on neotropical freshwater fish.	deforestation, mercury, oil spills, roads, siltation	Mining has resulted in direct and indirect losses of fish diversity in several Neotropical water bodies. Negative impacts on ichthyofauna can alter the structure of communities, jeopardize entire food chains and erode the ecosystem services provided by freshwater fish.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1agPCzaPQ4ArjmhOzs04HbqTmdA3_d6ZX/view?usp=share_link	A
2	Science of Total Environmental	The impacts of mining on the sovereignty and food security of indigenous peoples and local communities: a global review	2022	Blanco, Graziela Dias; Fernández-Llamazares, Álvaro; Branco, Gabriela Dias; Baker, Janelle; Tagliari, Mario Sérgio M.; Hayata, Maiara Albuquerque; Campos, Mari Lúcia; Hanazaki, Natália	This study aims to assess whether factors such as mining, trace element contamination, social inequality, lack of environmental policies and practices and socio-environmental conflicts directly impact the food sovereignty of IPLCs around the world.	ecotoxicology, ethnecology, food security, mining, rural communities	The results reveal that the combination of mining, social inequality and weak environmental strategies negatively interfere with the food sovereignty of IPLCs.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1trydEtKBP1vXWDxLzwpDZJ_s8CuaT5r1B/view?usp=share_link	M
3	Frontiers in Public Health	Social Sciences in One Health: Insights from Multiple World Perspectives on the Brumadinho Dam Break - Brazil	2021	Brandão, Ana Pérola Drulla; Sussai, Stefanie; Germiné, Jéssica Alves de Limac; Eltz, Diego Duarted; Araújo, Aline	As a starting point, we explored the recent case of a tailings dam collapse, considering how and why this event was experienced in different ways by the indigenous and non-indigenous worlds affected.	alternative-economy, equivocation, extractivism, indigenous-worlds, one-health, perspectivism, pluriverse, transdisciplinarity	Discussions from the social sciences should be incorporated, considering how to relate practice to the multiple realities in which a given problem or conflict is inserted. Overcoming the barriers that prevent transdisciplinary dialog is fundamental and urgent for an effective approach to the multiple and distinct interconnections between humans, animals and environments.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Mc65bl55AMv2-OnllznCGUjzL_jlowQ0/view?usp=share_link	B
4	Computational Science and Its Applications - ICCSA 2020 - 20th International Conference Cagliari, Proceedings, Part VII	Dam Rupture and Human Disaster: Córrego do Feijão, Brumadinho, MG	2020	Pedro Benedito Casagrande, Maria Giovana Parisi, Ana Clara Mourão Moura, Lourdes Marresa Camargos, Camila Marques Zyngier, Viviane da Silva Borges Barbosa, Danilo Marques de Magalhães and Gilberto Rodrigues da Silva	A study and characterization of the area was carried out to understand the flow of water, and consequently the mud. In addition, it was possible to obtain information on the land use of the area before and after the breach using supervised remote sensing image classification (Sentinel-2A).	mina-Córrego-do-Feijão, dam-break, land-use planning	Through a spatial and temporal analysis, it was estimated that the mud reached a total of 2.48 km ² , with the robust vegetation class being the most affected by the disaster in numerical terms. The typology of anthropic areas, despite being the smallest area affected by the mud, suffered the greatest impact.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1RX4Wwt19Pm575-gcbca7nqvYalZUm8k/view?usp=share_link	B
5	Revista Curso de Direito UNIFOR	Liabilities arising from environmental disasters in Minas Gerais	2020	da Costa, DSC; Barbosa, KFM; Bastos, MA; de Oliveira, SF;	With this in mind, this study aims to analyze two environmental disasters that have occurred in Minas Gerais in the last four years as a result of dam collapses, making a critical analysis of their socio-environmental consequences and the incidence of civil, criminal and administrative liability in the cases in question.	environmental-disaster, environmental-law, tragedy-of-Mariana-and-Brumadinho	It is noted that the data was obtained through documentary research, with theoretical in-depth study, mainly in books, case law, articles, news and reports on the damage caused. In the end, the aim is to show that this is not a mere accident of an unforeseeable nature, This is not a mere accident of an unforeseeable nature, which would exempt the company, its parent companies and the state from any blame or malice, since, in fact, there is a weakness in the supervision and safeguarding of the environment, generating and safeguarding of the environment, thus generating damage of a patrimonial and off-balance sheet nature to countless citizens	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1E908Karyh7OIkDPdYWwxKZHvbMslZk/view?usp=share_link	B
6	Desenvolvimento e Meio Ambiente UFFR	Relations between health and the environment: potential impacts resulting from the collapse of tailings dams - a review of the literature on the cases of Mariana and Brumadinho, MG	2022	da Silva, FL , Cunha-Santino, MB , Fushita, Á.T. , Miminel, VA , Bianchini, I.	Through a literature review, we searched for impacts of ore tailings that have affected human health and natural ecosystems.	human-health, natural-ecosystems, Mariana, Brumadinho, dam-rejects	There have been alterations to the metabolism and functioning of natural ecosystems, due to the contamination of environmental compartments and damage to biodiversity. In terms of human health, there were risks of poisoning, damage to mental health, aggravation of existing diseases, arboviruses and zoonoses.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1d0zj25SGxMp_g_FK10lahaZxP2EC-Cs/view?usp=share_link	A
7	Revista Ceres Viçosa	Carbon and Nitrogen Stocks under Different Land Uses in the Paraopeba River Basin-MG before the collapse of the Córrego do Feijão dam	2022	da Silva, LJ; de Carvalho Vicente, M; Louzada, JR; Durães, DA; Baldotto, LEB; da Silva, DD; Viana, MCM; Baldotto, MA	This study was carried out before the collapse of the Córrego do Feijão dam and aimed to evaluate and quantify the stocks of carbon, nitrogen and the C/N ratio in soils around the Paraopeba river basin in five regions corresponding to the upper, middle and lower reaches of the river, considering three factors of use: forest, pasture and tree forest, correlating them with the chemical and physical properties of the soil, with a view to interpreting past use in order to obtain strategies for ecosystem management and conservation.	soil-chemistry, organic-matter, management-and-conservation-of-ecosystems	The results indicate a significant variation in carbon and nitrogen stocks as the 20-40 cm layer increases. In terms of type of use, the forestry system was the most efficient in terms of carbon accumulation. Regarding the site, the regions of Brumadinho and Fortuna de Minas showed similarities in the incorporation of carbon into the soil, differing from the regions of Jeceaba, Florestal and Três Marias.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/18HCyxcX8LwZyTrc4amcywayyO9ANM/view?usp=drive_link	B

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8	Cadernos de saúde Pública	From Samarco in Mariana to Vale in Brumadinho: mining dam disasters and Collective Health	2019	de Freitas, CM; Barcelos, C.; Asmus, CIRF; da Silva, MA; Xavier, DR	The aim of this article is to present and discuss the complexity of these types of events for Public Health and the SUS, with reference to recent disasters.	-----	Not only should the Sendai Framework principle of better and safer reconstruction for the affected communities, but Collective Health and the SUS must actively participate in these processes, because depending on how they are carried out or even procrastinated by the companies that caused the disasters, they can reduce or increase the risks health risks in the medium and long term.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1d1d3GcYCRtdz7HCDI-fb-DopDulE2pB/view?usp=drive_link	B
9	Chasqui. Revista Latinoamericana de Comunicación	Urban socio-environmental risk and ore containment dams in digital newspapers in Brazil	2020	De Lima, MRD; Colatusso, VDW; Colatusso, RA	To analyze how three digital newspapers, Brasil de Fato, HuffPostBrasil and Nexo, presented the risks arising from these projects and stimulated the mobilization of the affected communities, since we assume that journalism should motivate society to participate in public life.	environmental-crisis, risks-and-vulnerability, mining, risk-framing, web-journalism, environment-and-development, dam-safety, mobilization	After presenting and analyzing the results, we concluded that the articles present three main risk frameworks: technological, socio-environmental and, residually, agency, with only one of the newspapers playing a role in mobilizing the population.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/15OIP49byCYy0EZIsBYNo_YmD6OAEUGzR/view?usp=drive_link	B
10	International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology	Assessment of the water quality of the Paraopeba River (Minas Gerais, Brazil) after the tailings dam collapse	2022	Fonseca, FV; Linhares, AMF; Silva, JRP; Silva, LLS; Bassin, ID; Bassin, JP; Kronemberger, FA; Habert, AC; Borges, CP	Water quality was monitored in 336 km of this river for 1 year immediately after the accident to assess the impact of the dam collapse by analyzing 33 physical-chemical parameters and toxicity at two trophic levels.	environmental-disaster, environmental-monitoring, subject-mining, river-water, surface-water-quality, toxicity	The indices showed that the tailings from the dam collapse had a considerable impact on the water quality of the Paraopeba River at first, immediately after the disaster, but that it decreased over time, illustrating a certain regeneration of the river in terms of the quality of the water column.	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13762-022-04430-2	B
11	CAMPO-TERRITÓRIO: revista de geografia agrária,	Valley of mud, river of stories: a geographical expedition in the context of the mining disaster in the Paraopeba river basin, Minas Gerais	2020	Gonçalves, RJ de AF	Held between February 4 and 6, 2019, the expedition in the Paraopeba River basin allowed direct contact with territories and subjects impacted by the mud-reject.	Brumadinho, river-Paraopeba basin, mining, disaster	Based on direct observations and interviews, the results highlight the cartography of the disaster along the river valley, with effects on the organization of life and work of life and work of farmers, fishermen and river dwellers. In short, it is believed that the reports of the field experience highlighted in the text will contribute to the critical debate on the mining model in Brazil.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1nN7yYXcz44yKW1miD73IfuFlgZaPHb/view?usp=drive_link	A
12	Revista Agrogeoambiental	Spatial and temporal analysis of the tailings dam collapse in Brumadinho, Brazil	2020	Leopoldino, JD; dos Anjos, CS; Simões, DP; Fernandes, LFR	This paper aims to assess the extent of the area affected by the collapse of Vale's tailings dam at the Córrego do Feijão mine in the municipality of Brumadinho, Minas Gerais, on January 25, 2019, which caused an environmental impact that will be felt for years to come.	remote-sensing, environmental-impact, digital-image-processing	The result was an area of 2.964096 m ² , from the dam to the Paraopeba River	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1YWZMOXmCW0CUZp029qq4Dtm1SqtKfFtl/view?usp=drive_link	B
13	Novos Cadernos NAEA	When the river is no longer worth it: the dilemma of Paraopeba river communities after the Brumadinho disaster	2022	Melo, TL; Medeiros, RD; Teixeira, RC	The research the consequences of the disaster of the collapse of the Vale dam and its effects its effects, particularly on the contamination of the Paraopeba River, which is used by the residents of the residents of the camp.	violation-of-rights, Vale, disasters, environmental-injustice, rio-Paraopeba, Covid-19	The results of the study point to the irreparable damage to the survival, daily life and health of the residents, as well as deepening the of marginalization and vulnerability.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1VTxYOu-7TtL8cwrKzRp9GfS21tsz8G/view?usp=drive_link	A
14	Science of Total Environmental	A partial least squares path model of environmental degradation in the Paraopeba River, for the rainy seasons after the collapse of the B1 tailings dam, Brumadinho, Brazil	2022	Mendes, RG; do Valle Júnior, RF; de Melo Silva, MMAP; de Moraes Fernandes, GH; Fernandes, LFS; Fernandes, ACP; Pissarra, TCT; de Melo, MC; Valera, CA; Pacheco, FAL	The aim of this study was to investigate the collapse of the B1 tailings dam at the Córrego do Feijão mine, which drastically affected the Brumadinho region (Minas Gerais, Brazil).	dam failure, iron ore waste, metal(oid)s, river contamination, NDVI changes, structural-equation modeling	The modeling results suggested a relationship between the turbulence of the river flow and the increased release of arsenic from the sand fractions, as well as the desorption of Mn from metal oxides, both of which represent causes of reduced water quality. They also revealed increasing concentrations of iron affecting the NDVI (greenness) of the forest, which was interpreted as environmental degradation.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1pIdXAU Pkp7vMIsA2E-CqL_nes-DkTtLD8/view?usp=drive_link	B
15	Ciência e cultura - Brumadinho/Artigos	Dam rupture in Brumadinho and access to water for affected communities: a human rights case	2020	Neves-Silva, P.; Heller, L.	This paper discusses the Brumadinho dam collapse and the human right to water.	-----	Empowering local communities so that they can fight for their rights and not be at the mercy of corporate and government decisions is a step forward. at the mercy of corporate and government decisions, is an important step towards preventing further tragedies. important step to avoid further tragedies	https://drive.google.com/file/d/13wO7mSDvsVlIACLM1Faf3Ri0EYfPzXII/view?usp=drive_link	M

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16	Science of Total Environmental	Threats and challenges to water security after the collapse of large tailings dams	2022	Pacheco, FAL; de Oliveira, MD; Oliveira, MS; Libânio, M.; do Valle Júnior, RF; de Melo Silva, MMAP; Pissarra, TCT; de Melo, MC; Valera, CA; Fernandes, LFS	The general objective of this study was to examine the collapse of the B1 tailings dam on the Ferro-Carvão stream, which contaminated the main watercourse (Paraopeba River) with 2.8 Mm3 of metal-rich tailings. The specific objective was to assess the percentage of non-compliant concentrations after the event, taking into account COPAM/CERH-MG Normative Deliberation no. 1.	tailings-dam breach, Paraopeba river, non-compliant-concentrations, seasonality, water-treatability, water-safety	The results showed non-compliant concentrations of aluminum, iron, manganese, lead, phosphorus and turbidity, clearly above the pre-rupture averages, especially during the rainy season. The catastrophe caused the Paraopeba River to be suspended as a source of drinking water for the Belo Horizonte Metropolitan Region (RMB; 6 million people).	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1LaZ9mc93mZuNl0REa0-IUVbksNZCivXF/view?usp=drive_link	B
17	Science of Total Environmental	Prognosis of metal concentrations in sediments and water of the Paraopeba River after the collapse of the B1 tailings dam in Brumadinho (Minas Gerais, Brazil)	2022	Pacheco, FAL; do Valle Júnior, RF; de Melo Silva, MMAP; Pissarra, TCT; Carvalho de Melo, M.; Valera, CA; Sanches Fernandes, LF	This study assessed the contribution of tailings to sediment and water contamination by these metals.	contamination, predictions, river water, sediment, tailings dam collapse, time-series analysis	Preliminary results from the Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average models predict Paraopeba's return to a pre-collapse condition in 7 to 11 years.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1KegzREIvXREM3IR-RlzzcmjqlMDmM4/view?usp=drive_link	B
18	Vector-Borne and Zoonotic Diseases	Infectious disease risks and vulnerabilities after an environmental disaster in Minas Gerais, Brazil	2020	Parekh, FK; Sim, KB; Olinger, G.; Ribeiro, FA	The effect of environmental disasters like this is felt in various sectors, damaging ecosystems in agriculture, wildlife and human communities.	Brazil, disasters, epidemiology, mosquito-borne, vector-borne	Environmental disasters cause significant disruption to ecosystems, flooding, contamination of water supplies and displacement of human populations, which can result in increased transmission and outbreaks of mosquito-borne and zoonotic diseases that can become a serious, long-term public health problem for the region.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/11QKdblncmpyIqb815XwqacQIXNER0xA/view?usp=drive_link	B
19	Environmental Research	First year after the Brumadinho tailings' dam collapse: Spatial and seasonal variation of trace elements in sediments, fishes and macrophytes from the Paraopeba River, Brazil	2021	Parente, CEI; Lino, AS; Carvalho, GO; Pizzochero, AC; Azevedo-Silva, CE; Freitas, MO; Teixeira, C.; Moura, RL; Ferreira Filho, VJM; Maln, O.	The aim of this study was to assess trace element contamination (As, Al, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Hg, Mn, Ni, Pb and Zn) in sediments, fish and macrophytes along the Paraopeba River, upstream and downstream of the dam breach site, during the dry and rainy seasons.	heavy-metals toxic-elements, human-health-risks, environmental-assessment	In addition, the concentrations of As and Pb exceeded the safe limit for fish consumption in 3% and 41% of the samples, respectively, representing a public health problem.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1iAbEZYh7Cn1WJld357xwAK_vB8dARyx/view?usp=drive_link	A
20	Ciência e cultura - Brumadinho/ Artigos	The Brumadinho disaster and the possible impacts on health. Mining disasters in Brazil: a case study of the dam ruptures in Mariana and Brumadinho	2020	Peixoto, SV; Asmus, CIRF	This article focuses on (1) effects on health conditions, (2) exposure to contaminants and health conditions, and (3) actions and future prospects.	-----	It is important to follow the evolution of these conditions over time, in order to provide systematized information to the local health service and contribute to the organization of this service, so that it can adequately meet the demand of the population living in the municipality.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1kwqDyzuO_9MscBHMW66OhC_qTuXcMonu/view?usp=drive_link	A
21	Case Studies in the Environment	Mining disasters in Brazil: a case study of the dam ruptures in Mariana and Brumadinho	2021	Primo, PPB; Antunes, MN; Ramos, MP; Arias, ARL; Oliveira, AE; Siqueira, CE	This case report describes the ruptures of the Mariana dam in 2015 and the Brumadinho dam in 2019, as well as their causes and consequences.	disaster, risk communication	Faced with this lack of communication and seeking answers and strategies to guarantee a space capable of expanding access to information in an up-to-date and reliable way for the population of the affected territories, we developed the Disaster Information Monitoring System (SIGDesastre).	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1fRWfM0UXsingtoqP16kDDFZEMCPZ73wq/view?usp=drive_link	B
22	Anais do Simpósio Brasileiro de Geoinformática	Spatial data management in the Brumadinho Project UFMG	2021	Santana, IL; Pinheiro, MB; Nicolau, LA; Davis, CA, Jr.; Graça AJS; Vinhas L.	The aim is to establish a neutral and public environment for organizing and providing unrestricted access to all the data from court cases, considered to be in the public good by the Court, to researchers and society in general.	-----	This paper presents the architecture developed to maintain the Platform with high availability, usability and meeting the requirements of public access to information, with an emphasis on data management aspects through a spatial data infrastructure.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1eupExAMr5mbIEV3XT5Uba7A0ux7bFLM/view?usp=drive_link	B
23	Sustainability in Debate	The impact of the Brumadinho dam collapse on the Naó Xohã village	2019	Silva, AA; Lunas, DAL; Dos Santos Bicalho, PS; MacIel, RMT	Among so many social groups affected by this announced tragedy, the reality of the Naó Xohã village, whose population lives on the banks of the Paraopeba River, also victimized by this environmental disaster, the consequences of which have yet to be seen.	Brumadinho, dams, territorialities, indigenous-rio-Paraopeba, Pataxó people	The proposal, however, is based on an interdisciplinary approach to the subject, which is the impact of the collapse of the Brumadinho dam on the Naó Xohã village, mainly due to the pollution that has spread into the Paraopeba river. To this end, a fruitful dialog was established between history, geography, economics and environmental issues.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Hjy4Up47y0-Ifw8ImB04wATunU-Gqkqxl/view?usp=drive_link	B
24	Science of Total Environmental	Severe impacts of the Brumadinho dam collapse (Minas Gerais, Brazil) on the water quality of the Paraopeba River	2020	Thompson, F; de Oliveira, BC; Cordeiro, MC; Masi, BP; Rangel, PT; Paz, P.; Freitas, T.; Lopes, G.; Silva, BS; S. Cabral, A.; Soares, M.; Lacerda, D.; dos Santos Vergilio, C.; Lopes-Ferreira, M.; Lima, C.; Thompson, C.; de Rezende, CE	Carry out biogeochemical, microbiological and ecotoxicological analyses on 464 km of the Paraopeba River in the week following the disaster (February 1, 2019) and four months later (May 27-29, 2019).	Brumadinho-dam, mining-disaster, rio-paraopeba, water-quality	Our study suggests that independent monitoring programs are needed to quantify the extent of the potential impacts caused by anthropogenic use of the river and promote the recovery of the impacted area.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1PvYdsXa43YHtGERSXEXMKyogFpsDRpU/view?usp=drive_link	M

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25	Relatórios Científicos	Metal concentrations and biological effects of one of the biggest mining disasters in Brazil	2020	Vergílio, CS; Lacerda, D.; Oliveira, BCV; Sartori, E.; Campos, GM; Pereira, ALS; Aguiar, DB; Souza, TS; Almeida, MG; Thompson, F.; Rezende, CE	The aim of this study is to evaluate the concentrations of multiple elements and the biological effects on the waters and sediments of the Paraopeba River after the collapse of the Brumadinho dam.	-----	The differences in metal concentrations in water and sediment between the upstream and downstream sides of the dam illustrate the effect of the tailings on the Paraopeba River. Toxicological tests showed that the water and sediments were toxic to different trophic levels, from algae to micro-crustaceans and fish. Fish exposed to water and sediments containing mine ore also accumulated metals in their muscle tissue. This assessment emphasizes the need for long-term monitoring in the affected area.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1jeRaucBpU1gZg0g9oubsTejuggxSGAH3/view?usp=drive_link	B
26	Revista Brasileira de Epidemiologia	Brumadinho Health Project: food and nutrition insecurity versus socioeconomic statuses and dimensions of the food system after the dam rupture	2022	Mariana Souza Lopes; Patricia Pinheiro de FreitasMary Anne Nascimento-SouzaSérgio Viana PeixotoAline Cristine Souza Lopes	To describe the food insecurity situation of families according to socio-economic characteristics and dimensions of the food system in Brumadinho, Minas Gerais, Brazil, after the disaster.	structural collapse, man-made disasters, socio-economic factors, health, food and nutrition security	The prevalence of food insecurity was high, with reports of a reduction in household income after the dam burst. In addition, many of the households had poorer structural quality and sewage disposal. These results highlight the vulnerability of the families and the possible violation of the human right to adequate food, denoting the urgency of ongoing remedial actions.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/16YxN2jnyV9jSW1RnCx923M0_pK7bVyh7/view?usp=drive_link	A